

Active Learning with Deep Support Vector Data Description for Earth Observation Satellite Image Classification

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Abstract—This paper presents a novel Active Learning (AL) framework that integrates deep Support Vector Data Description (SVDD) for optical satellite image classification. By defining a decision boundary within the deep SVDD model, we implement and iteratively update AL strategies based on this boundary to select the most informative samples for labeling. Our approach significantly reduces the need for labeled data while maintaining high classification accuracy. We evaluate our framework on the EuroSAT dataset using both RGB and Multispectral (MS) bands, demonstrating that our AL strategies namely, Most Similar, Top-K, and Bottom-K can effectively approximate the performance of a model trained on the full dataset with a fraction of the samples. The Top-K and Bottom-K strategies, in particular, show remarkable efficiency in querying informative samples. This study advances the application of AL in RS, offering a cost-effective solution for high-dimensional Earth Observation data analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep learning (DL) has emerged as a pivotal methodology within the machine learning (ML) landscape, offering numerous applications and benefits across diverse domains, including the analysis of Remote Sensing (RS) data. A thorough examination of existing studies reveals DL's proficiency in tackling complex classification problems and extracting high-level, intrinsic features from data [1]. However, one of the paramount challenges in supervised ML algorithms, including DL, is the labor-intensive and costly process of data labeling, which necessitates a substantial volume of training samples.

The application of deep neural networks (DNNs) to analyze RS images faces significant challenges, primarily due to two factors. First, multispectral satellite images encompass high-dimensional data, necessitating a large feature space for analysis. Second, the creation of an extensive dataset is complicated by the combination of images from satellites due to temporal variations in land cover [2].

Fig. 1: AL block diagram

Active Learning (AL) emerges as a powerful solution to address the challenges of DL in RS image analysis by maximizing the utility of limited labeled data. The core principle of AL is that a machine learning algorithm can achieve higher accuracy with fewer training labels through selective engagement in the learning process. This is accomplished by iteratively identifying and labeling the most informative samples from an unlabeled dataset, thereby optimizing learning efficiency. The AL process typically involves training a model, such as Support Vector Data Description (SVDD), on updated query samples iteratively and then applying it to the unlabeled pool to find the most informative samples, which are ranked based on their distance score (see Fig. 1).

The selection process in AL prioritizes samples based on their relevance and ambiguity, as determined by the model's output. These selected samples are then labeled, often by human annotators, and incorporated into the training set, allowing the model to be retrained with an enriched dataset. This interactive training approach not only accelerates the learning process but also enhances efficiency by focusing on samples that significantly contribute to the model's training. Studies

have demonstrated that AL-based approaches outperform traditional methods in various RS tasks, including wetland mapping and debris detection, highlighting the effectiveness of this technique in improving the accuracy and efficiency of satellite image analysis.

This paper presents a novel AL framework for multispectral satellite image classification. Our methodology leverages uncertainty sampling and diversity-based query strategies to iteratively select the most informative and diverse samples for labeling. We evaluate our approach on both RGB and Multispectral (MS) datasets and demonstrate significant improvements in classification accuracy compared to traditional supervised learning methods, while requiring substantially fewer labeled samples. The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- A novel AL framework for satellite image classification that combines uncertainty sampling and diversity-based query strategies.
- Leveraging deep SVDD by using AL strategies for one-class classification and anomaly detection.
- Insights and analysis on the impact of different AL strategies on the overall performance.

II. RELATED WORKS

The concept of AL has been explored in various contexts, with its roots tracing back to the seminal work in [3], which demonstrated its efficacy in reducing the amount of labeled data required for training models. In the context of image processing, AL has been applied to tasks such as object recognition and scene classification, showing promising results. However, classic approaches mainly include uncertainty sampling, which selects samples based on the confidence of the model's predictions, and query-by-committee, which compares the disagreement of an ensemble of models.

In the context of RS, AL has been applied to hyperspectral image classification, for instance [4] incorporates a dual learning-based siamese network (DLSN) and an adversarial uncertainty-based AL (AUAL) method to efficiently enhance feature distribution learning and then exploits an inter-class uncertainty AL. In addition, AL offers several benefits for change detection. For instance, [5] has shown that by actively selecting informative samples to label, AL can achieve the same change detection performance as a model trained on a large pre-annotated dataset while requiring fewer labeled samples.

Relevance Feedback is a mechanism used in the AL process to improve the performance of image retrieval systems [6]. Some researchers [7], [8] have contributed to the development and implementation of Relevance

Feedback mechanisms to create more efficient and effective retrieval systems. For instance, [9] discusses the use of Relevance Feedback in the context of semantic image retrieval, where the system learns from the user's feedback to improve the semantic similarity of the retrieved images.

Prior work typically addresses single-modality data, while our approach specializes in handling multispectral satellite imagery with numerous spectral bands. We draw from RS AL literature insights, introducing innovative techniques tailored to multispectral data challenges. Our uncertainty sampling method considers spectral and spatial diversity, ensuring a balanced selection of informative samples. Additionally, we propose a batch selection strategy that mitigates redundancy between samples, avoiding queries on visually similar patches.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our methodology employs an AL framework that integrates deep SVDD (as shown in Fig. 1) for the classification of multispectral satellite images. The AL framework is designed to efficiently utilize labeled data and reduce the annotation burden by selectively querying the most informative samples from an unlabeled pool. The process is iterative, with the model's performance improving as it learns from newly labeled data.

Fig. 2: The proposed method block diagram

A. Pre-training Phase

The AL framework begins with a pre-training phase where an initial query set of labeled samples is used to train an Autoencoder (AE). The AE learns to generate low-dimensional embeddings of the input data, capturing the salient features necessary for effective image representation. Concurrently, the SVDD model (the Encoder) is trained to establish a decision boundary that encapsulates the normal data distribution in the embedding space.

Let X and X' be the batch of query samples and the archive samples in the unlabeled pool including all classes, respectively. X' is used only in the selecting phase and does not interfere with the pre-training phase. In the first step, the AE consists of the symmetrical encoder, ϕ , and decoder, θ , and is trained by X . The objective of the AE is to optimize the network weights W_ϕ and W_θ by minimizing the reconstruction distance that is defined by:

$$\min_{W_\phi, W_\theta} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|x_i - \theta(\phi(x_i; W_\phi); W_\theta)\|_2^2 \quad (1)$$

where X is the batch of query sample and each sample is denoted x_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where n is the size of the batch.

We find c by feeding query samples to the pre-trained network and then calculating the mean values of the network's outputs, as formulated in the following equation:

$$c = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \phi(x_i; W_\phi). \quad (2)$$

B. AL Cycle

Upon training the AE model, SVDD (pre-trained encoder) is jointly trained to map the data into the smallest hyper-sphere and learns useful feature representations of the query class samples. The classifier network's weights W are initialized by the weights of the pre-trained decoder W_ϕ . The network's objective is to optimize the network weights W by minimizing the distance of embedding from c which is defined by the following equation:

$$\min_W \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\phi(x_i; W) - c\|^2. \quad (3)$$

The trained SVDD with initial query samples is applied to the unlabeled pool of samples, X' . The SVDD generates embeddings for each sample and computes the distance by the following equation:

$$s(x'_i) = \|\phi(x'_i; W) - c\|^2 \quad (4)$$

where $s(x')$, the distance of each sample from c in latent space, can be used as a measure for ranking the unlabeled samples. These distances are utilized to rank the samples according to their deviation from the normal data distribution. The lowest score represents the most relevant (normal) sample and the highest score is the most ambiguous (anomalous).

The ranking enables the selection of samples for Oracle querying using three distinct strategies: Most

similar, Top-K, and Bottom-K. The Most similar query strategy tries to find the representative samples that are close to c and we calculate as:

$$\Gamma_{M_k} := \{x'_i : [s(x'_i) < s(x'_j)]\} \quad (5)$$

s.t. $i \neq j$ and $|\Gamma_{M_k}| = k$

where Γ_{M_k} denotes the set of the k retrieved samples by the Most similar strategy. Also, two different samples of archive are denoted x'_i and x'_j for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, l$, where l is the number of the samples in unlabeled pool.

For the other two query strategies, we define M as the decision boundary where is the maximum distance of the normal samples in the hypersphere $M = [\max s(x_i)]$. The Top-K strategy selects samples with distances that are close to but less than M , targeting those that are most uncertain and potentially anomalous.

$$\Gamma_{T_k}^{(M,k)} := \{x'_i | x'_i \in X', s(x'_i) < M\}_{\text{top } k} \quad (6)$$

where Γ_{T_k} denotes the set of the k retrieved samples are less than M , and it specifies that these instances are ordered in such a way that those with distances closest to M are prioritized, without exceeding M . On the other hand, the Bottom-K strategy selects samples with distances that are close to M , focusing on those that are ambiguous yet likely to belong to the normal class.

$$\Gamma_{B_k}^{(M,k)} := \{x'_i | x'_i \in X', s(x'_i) > M\}_{\text{bottom } k} \quad (7)$$

where Γ_{B_k} denotes the set of the k retrieved samples by the Bottom-K strategy, focusing on instances whose distances from c are greater than M . Fig. 2 displays the block diagram for the suggested method. In the graphic, all three query techniques and M are mentioned. The selected samples are then presented to the oracle for labeling. The oracle, typically a human expert, provides the true labels for these samples. The newly labeled samples, referred to as "Updated Query Samples," are added to the training set, and the models are retrained with this augmented dataset.

C. Iterative Refinement

The AL cycle is repeated, with the model querying new samples in each iteration based on the updated decision boundary (M) and data distribution. This iterative process continues until a stopping criterion is met, which could be a performance threshold, a maximum number of iterations, or the exhaustion of the labeling budget.

Through this methodology, our AL framework aims to create a robust model for multispectral satellite image classification that requires fewer labeled samples while

Fig. 3: A sample of each class of the EuroSAT (RGB) dataset.

maintaining high accuracy and efficiency. The integration of deep SVDD with AL strategies allows for a nuanced selection of samples that balance uncertainty and representativeness, leading to a more effective learning process.

IV. RESULTS

The performance of our AL framework was rigorously evaluated on the EuroSAT [10] dataset. The benchmarked EuroSAT dataset has been used for recent studies in the RS field, in particular for the image classification task. We employed both RGB bands and multispectral bands for training and testing the network. The benchmark covers 13 spectral bands and comprises ten classes with a total of 27000 labeled and georeferenced images. Fig. 3 shows one sample of each class, chosen to describe the dataset visually.

The AL framework was implemented using three distinct query strategies: Most similar, Top-K, and Bottom-K. Each strategy was applied iteratively, with 25 new samples queried in each round until a total of 350 samples were labeled. The performance of each strategy was measured in terms of classification accuracy and compared against the baseline accuracy obtained when the model was trained with the full dataset of 5,000 samples (500 per class). Fig. 4 summarizes the AL performance results from both EuroSAT RGB and EuroSAT MS.

A. EuroSAT RGB

The EuroSAT RGB dataset chart depicted in 4a shows the accuracy of the model as a function of the number of labeled samples for three different AL strategies: Most Similar, Top-K, and Bottom-K. The Full Data baseline is represented by the red dashed line, indicating the model’s accuracy when trained on the entire dataset.

The Most Similar strategy (blue line) starts with lower accuracy but shows a steady increase as more samples are labeled, eventually approaching the Full

Data baseline. The Top-K strategy (orange line) demonstrates a more rapid increase in accuracy, surpassing the Most Similar strategy early on and closely tracking the Full Data baseline throughout the labeling process. The Bottom-K strategy (green line) shows a performance trend similar to the Top-K strategy, with both strategies nearly converging to the Full Data baseline as the number of labeled samples approaches 300.

B. EuroSAT MS

The EuroSAT MS dataset chart in 4b presents a similar comparison of the three AL strategies against the Full Data baseline.

The Most Similar strategy (blue line) again starts with lower accuracy but improves consistently as more samples are labeled, although it does not reach the Full Data baseline within the range of labeled samples shown. The Top-K strategy (orange line) shows a strong performance, with accuracy increasing sharply and surpassing the Most Similar strategy. It closely approaches the Full Data baseline, particularly in the latter half of the labeling process. The Bottom-K strategy (green line) exhibits a performance trend that is very similar to the Top-K strategy, with both strategies nearly

C. Comparison of AL Strategies and Datasets

Comparing the AL strategies across the two datasets, we observe the following: The Top-K and Bottom-K strategies consistently perform well in both the RGB and MS datasets, suggesting that these strategies are robust and effective across different types of data. The Most Similar strategy shows the least performance in the early stages of labeling but improves steadily, indicating that it may require more labeled samples to achieve high accuracy. The performance gap between the AL strategies and the Full Data baseline is smaller in the MS dataset compared to the RGB dataset. This suggests that the additional spectral information in the MS data may allow the AL strategies to more effectively approximate the performance of the Full Data baseline with fewer labeled samples.

In summary, the Top-K and Bottom-K strategies demonstrate strong and comparable performance in both the EuroSAT RGB and MS datasets, closely approximating the Full Data baseline with a limited number of labeled samples. The Most Similar strategy, while not as strong initially, shows potential with an increasing number of labeled samples. The results highlight the effectiveness of AL in reducing the labeling effort required to achieve high accuracy in multispectral satellite

(a) EuroSAT RGB

(b) EuroSAT MS

Fig. 4: AL Performance for three different strategies and accuracy by training the full data

image classification, with the MS data particularly benefiting from the AL strategies due to its richer spectral information.

V. CONCLUSION

The study contributes to the advancement of AL techniques in the RS domain and provides a practical solution to the challenges posed by data scarcity and labeling costs. The Top-K strategy, in particular, has shown to be robust across different types of data, closely approximating the performance of the Full Data baseline with a limited number of labeled samples. The Most Similar strategy, while not as strong initially, shows potential with an increasing number of labeled samples, especially in the multispectral context where it benefits from the richer spectral information.

The comparison between the EuroSAT RGB and MS datasets has highlighted the advantages of multispectral data in AL. The additional spectral bands in the MS data allow the AL strategies to achieve higher accuracy more quickly compared to the RGB data, emphasizing the potential benefits of multispectral data in RS applications. This insight underscores the importance of considering the type of data and its characteristics when designing and implementing AL strategies for satellite image classification.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S K Sudha and S. Aji, “An analysis on deep learning approaches: addressing the challenges in remote sensing image retrieval,” *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 42, pp. 9405 – 9441, 2021.
- [2] Elisabeth D. Hafner, Patrick Barton, Rodrigo Caye Daudt, Jan Dirk Wegner, Konrad Schindler, and Yves Bühler, “Automated avalanche mapping from spot 6/7 satellite imagery with deep learning: results, evaluation, potential and limitations,” *The Cryosphere*, 2022.
- [3] D. Cohn, L. Atlas, and R. Ladner, “Improving generalization with active learning,” *Machine Learning*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 201–221, 1994.
- [4] Xiyao Di, Zhaohui Xue, and Mengxue Zhang, “Active learning-driven siamese network for hyperspectral image classification,” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 15, no. 3, 2023.
- [5] Kaiyu Li, Xiangyong Cao, and Deyu Meng, “A new learning paradigm for foundation model-based remote-sensing change detection,” *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 62, pp. 1–12, 2024.
- [6] Omid Ghozatlou, Mihai Datcu, Adrian Focsa, Miguel Heredia Conde, and Silvia Liberata Ullo, “A review and a perspective of deep active learning for remote sensing image analysis: Enhanced adaptation to user conjecture,” *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, pp. 2–26, 2024.
- [7] Sudha S.K. and Aji S., “An active learning method with entropy weighting subspace clustering for remote sensing image retrieval,” *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 125, pp. 109107, 2022.
- [8] Julia Henkel, Genc Hoxha, Gencer Sumbul, Lars Möllenbrok, and Begüm Demir, “Annotation cost efficient active learning for content based image retrieval,” in *IGARSS 2023 - 2023 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 2023, pp. 4994–4997.
- [9] Jingwen Li, Yanting Cai, Xu Gong, Jianwu Jiang, Yanling Lu, Xiaode Meng, and Li Zhang, “Semantic retrieval of remote sensing images based on the bag-of-words association mapping method,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 13, 2023.
- [10] Patrick Helber, Benjamin Bischke, Andreas Dengel, and Damian Borth, “Eurosat: A novel dataset and deep learning benchmark for land use and land cover classification,” *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 2217–2226, 2019.